

SPIDER

EU-LAC Digital Partnership

D.5.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation – DEC Plan V1

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Meaning
BELLA	Building the Europe link to Latin America and the Caribbean
CELAC	Community of Latin American and Caribbean States
CoC	Community of Practice
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
DEI	Diversity, Equality and Inclusion
DIF	EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GEANT	Pan-European research and education network
LAC	Latin America and Caribbean countries
NREN	National Research and Education Network
RedCLARA	South American research & education network
R&I	Research and Innovation
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
STI	Science, Technology and Innovation
WG	Working Group

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SPIDER Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (DEC) Plan encapsulates our comprehensive strategy to amplify the impact of the project. Through targeted communication, strategic dissemination, and proactive exploitation of knowledge and results, we aim to reach key stakeholders, fostering understanding, creating awareness, and promoting digital cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean.

By identifying and understanding our target audiences, we tailor our efforts to resonate with their needs and aspirations. Our approach is not static but adaptive, recognizing the evolving landscape of society. We embrace flexibility, continually refining our strategies to maximize effectiveness and relevance.

With a clear roadmap in place, we set out to achieve our objectives with precision and purpose, thus every action is guided by our commitment to excellence and impact.

As we recognize that success is not measured solely by outputs but by outcomes, our key performance indicators provide a tangible framework for evaluating our progress, ensuring accountability, and driving continuous improvement.

The SPIDER DEC plan is not just a document but a living blueprint for success, evolving hand in hand with our journey. It comprises several key chapters, each playing a vital role in achieving our objectives:

1. **DEC Goals and Objectives:** This chapter outlines the overarching goals and objectives of our communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts, and provides a clear direction for our activities.
2. **Target Audiences:** In this chapter, we identify and analyse our target audiences, crucial for tailoring our efforts to effectively reach and engage with key stakeholders across Europe, LAC and beyond.
3. **Communication Strategy:** This chapter details our approach to communication, including the selection of communication channels, content production strategies, and the development of communication materials.
4. **Dissemination Strategy:** Similar to the communication strategy, this chapter outlines our approach to disseminating knowledge and project results and the channels that will be used to reach potential users of the project results.
5. **Exploitation Strategy:** In this chapter, we detail our strategy for exploiting project results and maximizing their impact, including key exploitation channels.
6. **Estimated Execution Timeline:** Provides an estimated timeline for executing communication and dissemination activities, ensuring timely implementation and coordination.
7. **Key Performance Indicators:** Outlines our key performance indicators (KPIs) for measuring the effectiveness of our communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts. Includes both quantitative and qualitative indicators.

The SPIDER DEC Plan is a roadmap that guides our vision for the amplification of the impact of the project. It is a dynamic document that will be continually updated to reflect our evolving strategies and insights. Main progress achieved in implementing this plan will be reported in the updated version of the DEC plan (D5.2), which will provide a comprehensive overview of our achievements and learnings throughout the project lifecycle.

1. DEC GOALS AND OBJETIVES

The SPIDER project continues the longstanding tradition of collaboration between the European Union and Latin America and the Caribbean in the realms of digital transformation and research and innovation (R&I). Its primary goal is to leverage the full potential of the BELLA network and implement the outcomes of EU-LAC dialogues within the context of digitalization and R&I. To achieve this, SPIDER unites relevant R&I stakeholders from both regions, forming a multidisciplinary consortium dedicated to realizing the project's objectives.

Within this framework, a comprehensive Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan will steer efforts to ensure the broadest possible impact of SPIDER's outcomes. This plan aims to foster EU-LAC partnerships, bolster visibility and reputation, facilitate knowledge exchange, and support policy development.

Through these strategic initiatives, SPIDER's stakeholders will actively engage in collaborative endeavours, provide insights for decision-making processes, and maximize the project's overall contributions.

As a pivotal component of the project, this DEC plan seamlessly aligns with the project's overarching vision and the specific objectives outlined in Work Package 5, which encompass the following:

- To develop a detailed Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) plan to promote SPIDER to target audiences.
- To establish SPIDER as an exciting and innovative EC-funded initiative supporting human-centred and sustainable digital transformation in LAC.
- To maximize the impact of SPIDER outcomes and create pathways to exploitation.
- To create synergies with BELLA network and other initiatives supporting dialogues on digital transformation.

As established by the European Research Executive Agency, dissemination, exploitation and communication are different but interlinked concepts¹. Thus, DEC activities sometimes overlap, as they serve different purposes. As such, the objectives for each strategy vary, but they are meant to work in harmony. A strong communication strategy will help the project become known among SPIDER's target audiences, thereby increasing its possibilities at disseminating generated knowledge and results in the future. On the other hand, a strong dissemination strategy will highlight the important work being carried out by the project and demonstrate the enrichment created by EU-funded projects. Together, communication and dissemination create the groundwork for exploitation and sustainability, which will be discussed in detail in D5.5 – Sustainability Plan, due in M30.

1.1. *Communication Objectives*

Aligning SPIDER's communicational efforts with the project's overall goals, actions, impact and stakeholders is crucial for establishing the tone for its visibility and credibility, and for effectively addressing and engaging target groups. Therefore, the following communication objectives were established:

¹ Dissemination and exploitation https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en; Guide on communication, dissemination and exploitation https://rea.ec.europa.eu/publications/communication-dissemination-exploitation-what-difference-and-why-they-all-matter_en; and Communicating about your EU-funded project https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en.

- Communicate and promote the SPIDER project and its objectives to generate momentum and portray the project as dynamic and innovative EU-LAC cooperation project.
- Engage target groups actively to maintain their interest and encourage continuous follow-up on project developments.
- Reach and engage diverse target groups, maximizing the project's impact and visibility.
- Position SPIDER as an EC-funded initiative at the forefront of EU-LAC collaboration in human-centred and sustainable digital transformation.
- Increase the awareness of the BELLA network to improve the exploitation of its full potential.

Lastly, all the communication efforts will help support the positioning of the following key messages:

- SPIDER embraces a digital world that revolves around people and sustainability by shaping a future where technology enhances lives while also upholds the inherent value and equality of every individual and the respect of the environment.
- The BELLA infrastructure is a gateway to new horizons that is paving the way for a digital era filled with growth, collaboration, and success.
- SPIDER is at the forefront of EU-LAC collaboration in digital transformation and R&I.
- SPIDER, as an innovative EC-funded initiative, is supporting a human-centred and sustainable digital transformation in LAC.

1.2. Dissemination Objectives

To disseminate the knowledge and findings of SPIDER effectively, enhance the project's influence and foster the progression of cutting-edge knowledge globally, SPIDER will undertake dissemination efforts aimed at achieving the following specific objectives:

- Implement targeted dissemination strategies to reach target audience through online and offline channels.
- Increase the visibility of project results through high-impact channels, such as project and third-party events, scientific publications, and institutional websites.
- Foster collaboration and knowledge exchange with stakeholders from diverse disciplines by disseminating project findings.
- Guarantee the visibility and accessibility of SPIDER's outcomes by publishing findings in open-access repositories and journals.

1.3. Exploitation Objectives

Exploitation efforts are guided by the objective to translate project results into tangible actions, reach potential users and stakeholders capable of advancing these outcomes, and foster the dissemination of valuable knowledge. Beyond the mere generation of findings or innovations, the focus lies on ensuring their practical utilization, engaging key stakeholders to drive progress, and facilitating widespread knowledge-sharing. Therefore, we have established the following objectives:

- Broadcast project results to relevant stakeholders, including policy makers, NRENs, RPOs, LAC space agencies and digital dialogues leaders.
- Facilitate knowledge transfer to ensure general adoption of project outcomes.
- Foster collaboration between NRENs, Policy Makers, RFOs, RPOs, digital dialogues leaders and the GEANT community, to promote the uptake of project results.

- Demonstrate the societal impact of EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.

2. TARGET AUDIENCES

Distilling our Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication plan for SPIDER needs a meticulous segmentation of our audience, aligning with the key stakeholders and beneficiaries impacted by its outcomes. This tailored approach ensures that our efforts are precisely directed, maximizing their effectiveness.

Given SPIDER's overarching objective of fostering the exploitation of the BELLA infrastructure's capabilities and advancing EU-LAC dialogues on R&I, it is critical to identify the primary audience groups. These include:

- **Regional and National Research and Education Networks:** Regional networks RedCLARA and GEANT interconnects the NRENs in both sides of the Atlantic. NRENs facilitate advanced communication and collaboration among research and education institutions within a region or country. They are vital for enabling high-speed data exchange and cooperation in research and education and work as the facilitators of the BELLA infrastructure, so they are a key audience of the SPIDER project since their involvement in this initiative is pivotal.
- **BELLA Network:** The BELLA network spans multiple countries and facilitate joint research initiatives. In addition to the NRENs involved in the development of BELLA (Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Spain, together with the regional networks RedCLARA and GEANT), BELLA's extended countries include Peru, El Salvador, Honduras, Guatemala, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Trinidad and Tobago, Jamaica, Cuba, Paraguay, Bolivia, Mexico, Belize, and Uruguay.
- **GEANT Community:** GEANT fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing among NRENs, user organizations, research, and educational institutions, as well as the commercial sector in Europe, therefore their involvement in SPIDER is keen in our DEC efforts as they are relevant players in the strengthening of the EU-LAC digital partnership.
- **Research, Funding, and Academic Institutions:** This segment involves Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs). RPOs include universities, research organizations, and centres of excellence, while RFOs provide funding for international cooperation programs, prioritizing thematic areas for research and innovation. Involving these institutions and tackling them effectively will help fully exploit the outcomes of the project and the potential of the BELLA network.
- **Policy Makers and Digital Dialogues Leaders:** This group includes policy makers at various levels, including government institutions, regional agencies, and bi-regional S&T cooperation agreements' actors. They engage in digital dialogues to shape policies and support intergovernmental cooperation in research and innovation. Thus they are important to address since they can benefit from the outcomes, roadmap, and recommendations to implement digital dialogues' commitments.
- **Digital and ICT Companies:** Encompassing a wide range of actors such as large corporations, SMEs, startups, and innovation hubs, digital and ICT companies play a pivotal role in driving digital transformation. They contribute expertise, resources, and innovation to advance technology solutions and foster economic growth, thus tackling them and engaging them with the outcomes of SPIDER will help the full exploitation of BELLA.
- **LAC Space Agencies:** These agencies, such as ALCE in Latin America and entities like the German Space Agency at DLR, utilize advanced network infrastructure like BELLA, so it is important to address them and create awareness among them about the potential of this infrastructure and how they could benefit from its exploitation.
- **Civil Society:** This encompasses civil society organizations and NGOs, along with the public. It represents the broader societal context within which digital

transformation and research initiatives operate, and lastly, the final beneficiaries of the outcomes and improvements that SPIDER can promote.

3. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

To bolster the established objectives of our communication strategy, we have developed a framework based on three foundational pillars. These pillars serve as guiding principles for our initiatives aimed at maximizing SPIDER's visibility and engagement with our target groups.

These pillars, identified as Launch and Connect, Build Momentum, and Increase Reach and Positioning, are intricately woven together to form a cohesive strategy aimed at achieving our communication objectives.

- **Launch and Connect:** The first pillar revolves around establishing SPIDER's brand identity, setting the tone for communication and visual representation. It encompasses the creation of the project's visual and communications identity, alongside the project website and the establishment of its social media channels. Subsequently, efforts will focus on introducing SPIDER and elucidating its objectives to target groups through the consortium's networks.
- **Build Momentum:** Once the project has established its online presence across pertinent channels, ensuring accessibility to our audience, SPIDER will work to increase awareness about its progress. It means actively showing that the project is dynamic and innovative, connecting with its target groups, highlighting the project progress, and getting noticed by its key target groups.
- **Increase reach and positioning:** To enhance SPIDER's reach, the project aims to actively engage partners and key stakeholders, encouraging their involvement to transform them into advocates and amplifiers of SPIDER's communications. By empowering these partners, the project's communication efforts can effectively broaden their impact, reaching a wider audience. This strategy will be executed through targeted email initiatives, social media campaigns, and web outreach, all tailored to engage our desired demographic. Through these concerted efforts, SPIDER's visibility and influence will be bolstered, solidifying its position within its sphere of operation.

3.1. Communication Channels

The selected channels have undergone careful curation to ensure the precise targeting of our intended audience and the effective dissemination of SPIDER's core messages. Each channel functions as a strategic conduit, facilitating meaningful and impactful engagement with our target demographic. These platforms will feature updates on the progress of the project, promotion of SPIDER's values, vision, impact, and consortium, as well as pertinent information aimed at enhancing our audience's understanding of the contextual needs SPIDER is addressing.

3.1.1. Website

The cornerstone of SPIDER's communication strategy resides in its website (www.spidernetwork.org), which serves as the comprehensive repository for all pertinent project information. Through its various sections, the website offers extensive and detailed insights into different facets of the project, facilitating a deeper understanding among our target audience. This platform not only articulates the project's key messages and positioning but also enhances SPIDER's credibility.

When developing the website, several key issues were considered to ensure optimal functionality and user experience. Firstly, emphasis was placed on implementing responsive design, ensuring seamless navigation and usability across various devices, including web and mobile platforms. A clear and intuitive navigation menu was included to aid user navigation, and each page features a consistent contact section at the end, comprising a newsletter subscription button and links to social media profiles to ease the user's access to more information about SPIDER.

Aesthetically, the goal was to create a modern, clean, and dynamic website that reflected the project's identity.

In line with this vision, the website was meticulously crafted with a structured layout comprising six pages, as follows:

Home: This page serves as the central hub, providing an overview of the project and its objectives. It offers convenient navigation to various sections of the website guiding users to explore further.

About SPIDER: Delving deeper into the project, this section offers comprehensive details regarding its objectives, description, and the SPIDER Consortium. Visitors can gain insights into the core mission of the project and its significance within the broader context.

The SPIDER Consortium: This page offers detailed information about the consortium's members, serving as a valuable resource for understanding the collaborative framework underpinning the project. It highlights the diverse expertise and partnerships involved, showcasing the collaborative efforts propelling SPIDER forward.

Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF): Acting as a platform for dialogues, this section promotes the forum, its members, objectives, and the two working groups that integrate with its goals: WG1 Human-Centric digital transformation and WG2 Diversity, Equality and Inclusion.

News: This section keeps visitors abreast of the latest developments and announcements related to the project. Users can access timely information such as press releases, event updates, and project milestones, ensuring they remain informed about SPIDER's progress.

Resources: This section offers supplementary materials and tools related to the project, providing reports, research findings, educational materials, and other resources to deepen understanding and support involvement in SPIDER.

Acknowledgement of the EU funding: In the footer of every single page of the project's website, we acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

3.1.2. Social media channels

To bolster the project's online visibility and broaden its reach, SPIDER will strategically maintain an active presence on LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter). These platforms serve as potent channels for communicating the project's key messages and engaging with the target audience effectively. By leveraging the dynamic features of LinkedIn and X, SPIDER aims to foster meaningful interactions, share valuable insights, and amplify its impact within the project's community and beyond. Through regular updates, engaging content, and strategic networking efforts, SPIDER will not only enhance its online presence but also drive traffic toward its website, ensuring that its mission and objectives resonate widely across diverse audiences.

[LinkedIn Profile](#)

[X profile](#)

3.1.3. Newsletter

To expand the project's reach and enhance its audience engagement, SPIDER will launch a newsletter distributed through email. This newsletter will serve as a direct communication channel to share project updates, milestones, and key messages with subscribers. Through insightful content, SPIDER aims to captivate the interest of its audience and drive traffic to its website. By leveraging the newsletter's reach and effectiveness, SPIDER will foster a sense of community among its subscribers, ensuring that they remain informed and involved in the project's journey.

3.1.4. Partners' networks and multipliers

SPIDER's partners possess an extensive and influential network within the realms of research and innovation across Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean. This robust network not only bolsters SPIDER's credibility and reputation but also serves as an opportunity to stretch the project's objectives and outcomes within relevant stakeholder communities. By leveraging these connections, SPIDER enhances its capacity to create a

meaningful impact, amplifying its reach and influence. Moreover, this network facilitates collaboration and knowledge exchange, empowering other experts and researchers, and contributing to the broader goals of SPIDER.

In line with this approach, is relevant to note that SPIDER Consortium, RedCLARA, and GEANT have signed a Memorandum of Understanding, solidifying their alliance and amplifying the impact of the BELLA infrastructure. This memorandum lays the groundwork for SPIDER-BELLA collaboration, with a focus on facilitating knowledge exchange through joint communication activities and participation in forums and events. This robust collaboration exemplifies the commitment of these entities to shaping the future of EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation and R&I.

3.1.5. Press and Media

The project will actively engage with diverse media outlets, including specialized, general, and local media, in order to effectively communicate SPIDER's project objectives across a wide spectrum of audiences. This approach ensures that SPIDER's message resonates not only with specialized groups but also reaches broader and localized communities. By tapping into various media channels, SPIDER can tailor its communication strategies to suit the interests and preferences of different audience segments. This comprehensive media outreach enhances SPIDER's visibility and fosters deeper connections with stakeholders at all levels, ultimately strengthening the project's impact and engagement across diverse sectors and regions.

In this manner, as an effort to increase SPIDER’s positioning, a Branded Content on the Spanish newspaper La Razón was published to broadcast the project and its impact among local readers of this well-known newspaper. The [online article](#) was published on March, 2024. Following some screenshots from this publication in Spanish:

“SPIDER busca reducir la brecha digital entre Europa y América Latina y el Caribe”

Grupo INMARK lidera este proyecto internacional apoyado en la puesta en marcha de la red BELLA, que ha incrementado la interconectividad de Europa, Latinoamérica y el Caribe

▲ Yolanda Úrsa, directora de Gestión de la Innovación de Grupo INMARK Fotografía: Carmen Solana Cires

LA RAZÓN

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SPIDER es un proyecto de cooperación internacional muy ambicioso que requiere un enfoque multidisciplinario, que sólo puede llevarse a cabo con un equipo experimentado. INMARK lidera y coordina el Consorcio SPIDER que incluye socios de España, Portugal, Alemania, Bélgica, Chile, Ecuador, Brasil y Costa Rica. Y, además, cuentan con el apoyo de RedClara, la red regional de Investigación y Educación de Latinoamérica. Conozcamos más del proyecto

Por eso nace SPIDER, para responder a la necesidad de aprovechar el potencial de la red BELLA y reducir la brecha digital que existe actualmente entre Europa y América Latina y el Caribe.

▲ Reunión en Madrid del consorcio de SPIDER Grupo INMARK

“Hoy en día, la cooperación internacional en investigación e innovación es fundamental para afrontar los desafíos globales”

¿Qué aplicaciones tendrá?

Este proyecto, con una duración de 30 meses, tendrá como resultado, por un lado, la creación de una hoja de ruta para fomentar la cooperación bi-regional en proyectos e iniciativas para la transformación digital. SPIDER quiere ser un proyecto de referencia para la expansión del ecosistema digital en América Latina desde la perspectiva de un desarrollo tecnológico alineado con los principios de diversidad, igualdad e inclusión.

3.1.6. Events

Project events

Seeking to support the project 's activities, while also launching and strengthening the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum, SPIDER will organize and host a series of co-creation and participatory events that seek to engage with relevant stakeholders through focus groups, workshops, webinars, demo days, pitching sessions, DIF related events and final conference event.

Event	Tentative Date
Online Focus group 1 - AI, Blockchain, Cloud Computing and 5G	09/2024
Online Focus group 2 - Cybersecurity and Virtual Research Environment (VRE)	10/2024
Online Focus group 3 - AI, Blockchain, Cloud computing and 5G	10/2024
Online Focus group 4 - Cybersecurity and Multiuser Virtual Environment (VRE)	10/2024
Online Focus group 5 - AI, Blockchain, Cloud Computing and 5G	10/2024
Online Focus group 6 - Cybersecurity and Multiuser Virtual Environment (VRE)	09/2024
DIF Annual event (hybrid), in the framework of TICAL 2024	Rio de Janeiro, 11/2024
Online Networking Event for the innovation hubs selected under the Twinning Programme (1)	10/2024
Online Networking Event for the innovation hubs selected under the Twinning Programme (2)	01/2025
Webinar/Workshop on digital maturity assessment for the start-ups and SMEs from the twinning programme	11/2024
Webinar/Workshop on go-to market strategies for the start-ups and SMEs from the twinning programme	02/2025
Online Demo-Day for 10 selected SMEs from the twinning programme	12/2024-06/2025
Final Twinning event	To be defined
Final conference	To be defined

Third-party events

To boost the project visibility, engage potential BELLA infrastructure users, and connect with stakeholders, the consortium actively participates in third-party events. Through presentations and networking, we communicate the project objectives and gather valuable

feedback. This engagement helps to proactively establish opportunities to connect, collaborate, and communicate.

	Event	Description	Date
1	Political Dialogue on Digital Governance	This gathering serves as a platform for policymakers, experts, and stakeholders to engage in substantive discussions regarding the intersection of politics and digital governance. Hosted in the frame of the EU-LAC Digital Alliance.	May, 2024
2	Political Dialogue on Data Governance	This dialogue provides a platform to exchange insights, share best practices, and develop strategies to effectively govern data in a rapidly evolving technological landscape. The Political Dialogue on Data Governance convenes policymakers, industry leaders, and experts to explore critical issues surrounding the management and regulation of data	October, 2024
3	Tical 2024	TICAL serves as a collaborative platform for Latin American and Caribbean research networks that are members of RedCLARA to exchange experiences and address challenges in leveraging digital technologies for socioeconomic development, aiming to shape a collective agenda for sustainable growth.	November, 2024
4	Political Dialogue on AI and Connectivity and Inclusion	The Political Dialogue on AI and Connectivity and Inclusion brings together policymakers, technologists, and advocates to address the multifaceted impacts of artificial intelligence (AI) and connectivity on society. This forum provides a platform for robust discussions on leveraging AI and enhanced connectivity to foster inclusion and equitable access to opportunities.	November, 2024
5	XXVIII Ibero-American Summit of Heads of State and Government	The XXVIII Ibero-American Summit of Heads of State and Government is a diplomatic gathering where leaders from Ibero-American countries convene to discuss pressing regional issues and strengthen cooperation. This summit serves as a platform for dialogue and collaboration on various topics, including economic development, social progress, and cultural exchange, among others. This summit will take place under the theme 'Innovation, Inclusion, and Sustainability.	November, 2024

3.2. Content Production for Communication Purposes

In pursuit of our communication objectives, content advertised across SPIDER channels will prioritize project updates, offering insights into SPIDER's vision, objectives, and activities. Additionally, our communication efforts aim to educate and raise awareness about the BELLA Network, illuminate the realities faced by research and innovation (R&I) communities, and spotlight the importance of EU-LAC digital partnerships.

To ensure coherence and value in our communication endeavours, we have established the following communication pillars as guiding principles for content creation. These pillars have been designed to provide consistency and deliver meaningful content that resonates with our audience:

- **About SPIDER:** At the heart of this pillar lies a comprehensive understanding of SPIDER's mission, objectives, and expected outcomes. These contents aim to reinforce the project's branding and positioning through contents that underpin SPIDER's visions.
- **Updates, milestones, and activities:** the updates pillar serves as a dynamic repository of SPIDER's progress and achievements, offering regular insights into its activities, milestones, and engagements. From updates on key meetings and significant milestones to the latest developments and publications, this section provides a comprehensive overview of SPIDER's journey.
- **Context and current state of EU-LAC digital partnership:** In the ever-evolving landscape of digitalization, this pillar provides valuable insights into the significance of this transformative direction, also it strengthens and makes visible the context that gives SPIDER a purpose and "reason-why". The topics that will be addressed within this pillar are: the BELLA network, the current state of digitalization, relevant concepts on digital transformation, issues associated with existing digital gaps, and more.

3.3. *Communication materials*

To strengthen SPIDER's visibility, credibility, and positioning, communication materials were designed to support the project's efforts to broadcast its activities and results while promoting its values and vision. Also, these materials pretend to align all the efforts that the consortium undertakes to spread the word about SPIDER and create strategic alliances while ensuring that the project identity remains consistent. The initial materials created are the following:

Logo

The brand identity for SPIDER is intricately tied to the project's fundamental values of collaboration, innovation, inclusion, sustainability, transparency, diversity, and digitalization. Positioned as a conduit between the EU and LAC regions and between technological progress and societal welfare, our selected logo symbolizes a commitment to sustainable and human-centred digital transformation. The colour palette and font choice serve to underscore our message, evoking modernity, innovation, and technological sophistication, while presenting a polished image.

To fully leverage this valuable resource across various backgrounds and dimensions, we developed a range of colour variations for both the logo and its accompanying isotypes. This ensures optimal visibility and adaptability in diverse contexts, enhancing the overall versatility and effectiveness of our brand identity.

Media Kit

The active participation and alignment of our partners with our communication endeavours are paramount to guarantee the successful execution of the project actions, as well as the amplification of the project's key messages. To facilitate this alignment and streamline communication efforts, we meticulously crafted a comprehensive Media Kit, which has been disseminated to all partners and potential collaborators. This kit serves as a comprehensive guide, detailing essential elements such as branding guidelines, including how to use logos and corporate colours effectively. Additionally, it provides insight into key messages and offers access to image stock resources, ensuring that all communications are not only aligned with our overarching strategy but also maintain consistency in visual identity and messaging across all platforms and channels.

Excerpts from this media kit can be found in Annex 1.

Background for online meetings

In order to fortify the project's identity and foster a cohesive sense of unity among partners and other pertinent stakeholders for our online meetings and events, we meticulously crafted a distinctive background emblematic of the project's identity. This background was added to Annex 2.

Project presentation

SPIDER's presentation was designed to deliver a visual narrative, showcasing the essence of the project, and serve as a versatile tool for partners to seamlessly introduce SPIDER at diverse events and networking platforms, amplifying our collective mission and fostering fruitful collaborations. This presentation is available in Annex 3.

4. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

To ensure SPIDER's results are effectively disseminated, the project will employ a strategic approach. Not only will it introduce the project to relevant stakeholders, but it will also position it as an innovative initiative strengthening EU-LAC cooperation in digital transformation and R&I.

Using a blend of online and offline channels, SPIDER will implement targeted dissemination strategies to engage diverse audiences. This involves leveraging social media, websites,

and email newsletters, while also recognizing the value of interactions through workshops, seminars, and events.

SPIDER emphasizes the importance of fostering collaboration. By disseminating its results and facilitating opportunities for dialogue and partnership, SPIDER aims to create a dynamic and inclusive environment where ideas can flourish.

SPIDER's dissemination strategy is structured around three core stages, seamlessly integrated with its communication plan for a coordinated approach.

In the **initial phase**, SPIDER will invest in communication efforts to establish a robust foundation for dissemination. Extensive outreach activities during the project's first year will familiarize stakeholders with SPIDER's mission and objectives, fostering receptivity among target audiences for subsequent phases.

Transitioning to the **second phase**, SPIDER will focus on disseminating its results to key stakeholders. Utilizing targeted email campaigns and active participation in conferences and events, SPIDER will strategically engage with its audience, ensuring its findings reach those poised to benefit the most. This phase represents a crucial moment where SPIDER's initial groundwork yields tangible dissemination opportunities.

The **final phase** will see SPIDER's efforts culminate in high-impact channels. Building upon earlier momentum, SPIDER will leverage its established authority to disseminate results through selected events and publications. Additionally, a final project event will provide a platform for the consortium to showcase conclusive results and share valuable insights gained throughout the project's duration.

4.1. Dissemination Channels

4.1.1. Email marketing platform

SPIDER will leverage the email marketing platform, MailChimp, to deliver targeted messages and updates directly to stakeholders. Through personalized email campaigns and newsletters, SPIDER will engage with key audiences to share project results and significant milestones.

4.1.2. Social media channels and website

The project will also use SPIDER social media platforms, such as X (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn, and website for dissemination purposes. These channels will help share project results and relevant content. By regularly posting engaging and informative content, SPIDER can reach a broader audience, encourage interaction, and drive traffic to its website for more in-depth information and resources. Additionally, social media platforms offer opportunities for direct engagement with stakeholders, facilitating dialogue, networking, positioning, and credibility.

4.1.3. SPIDER Community of Practice

The SPIDER Community of Practice will serve as a virtual space for stakeholders to connect, collaborate, and exchange knowledge and experiences. SPIDER will actively engage with community members, share project findings, gather feedback, and encourage participation.

in project-related activities. By cultivating a vibrant and interactive community, SPIDER can amplify its impact and extend its reach beyond the project boundaries.

4.1.4. Project Events

SPIDER will host Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) events and a final conference to engage directly with stakeholders and disseminate project results. Additionally, other project events, such as focus groups, workshops, webinars and twinning events, serve as platforms for raising awareness about SPIDER and attracting new collaborators and supporters. Through strategic event planning and execution, SPIDER can maximize its visibility, engagement, and impact within the research and innovation community.

4.2. Content Production for Dissemination Purposes

The content slated for dissemination aims to spotlight the findings of the project, crafting engaging material to effectively convey knowledge that relevant stakeholders can harness. This encompasses the documentation of project outcomes and the provision of accessible resources tailored to various stakeholders' needs. For instance, this could involve presenting insights from the EU-LAC digital ecosystem survey. Furthermore, the dissemination content will emphasize the utilization of tools and mechanisms set by SPIDER. These resources will be adaptable to suit different target groups, objectives, dissemination channels, and contextual factors. The range of content and tools will encompass, but not be restricted to, the following:

- **Guidelines for human-centred and sustainable EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation:** Through several publications on the SPIDER Website, social media, and newsletter, these guidelines will be promoted as well with the features and key elements identified to help remove barriers that hamper bi-regional cooperation on the ground.
- **Survey report on the digital ecosystem interconnectivity and the potential of the BELLA Infrastructure:** This report will be shared through website updates, social media posts, and email newsletters, to broadcast and highlight the main results and insights from the survey and identify what drives or hinders the use of the BELLA infrastructure and the current state of the EU-LAC interconnectivity.
- **Focus Group report on BELLA's potential for digital transformation:** Conveying the insights gathered from focus group discussions via our website, social media channels, and email newsletters through a report that illustrates strategies to foster a collaborative atmosphere conducive to leveraging the BELLA network and digital technologies. We'll highlight practical approaches and best practices to encourage active engagement and effective utilization of these resources.
- **Position paper on pathways for the exploitation of the BELLA infrastructure:** Actively promotion of the position paper through various channels, including email blasts, social media platforms, relevant events, and our newsletter. Additionally, we'll publish the paper on the SPIDER website and ensure its widespread visibility through promotion across our social media networks.
- **Roadmap for future EU- LAC cooperation on digital transformation:** Broadcasting this roadmap on the SPIDER website, social media platforms, and through targeted email campaigns. This roadmap highlights short and medium-term actions and available funding schemes essential for roadmap implementation and will be disseminated through a report and infographics.
- **EU-LAC Twinned digital innovation hubs action plans, services portfolio, and mapping of new business opportunities:** Share information on the Twinning programme action plans through newsletters, social media, and SPIDER's website, while also collaborating with digital innovation hubs to boost visibility for services portfolio and sharing best practice.

5. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

The evolution of SPIDER's exploration plan is tied to the project's progress, as the results obtained will shape the optimal strategies for leveraging them. The strategy is designed to adapt dynamically, ensuring alignment with emerging insights and opportunities to maximize impact.

Central to this adaptive approach is the aim to serve as a vital conduit between project outcomes and stakeholders, fostering collaborative efforts and catalysing EU-LAC cooperation in digital transformation and research and innovation. SPIDER recognizes the need for continuous refinement to facilitate seamless knowledge transfer, enabling stakeholders across sectors to grasp and effectively utilize project outcomes.

Strategic alliances with key stakeholders are crucial for amplifying the reach and effectiveness of SPIDER's initiatives, providing a robust foundation for ongoing collaboration. Leveraging the collective expertise and resources of these partnerships remains a cornerstone for maximizing project impact.

At its core, SPIDER's adaptive exploitation plan embodies principles of collaboration, innovation, and inclusivity. By continuously adjusting to bridge the gap between project outcomes and stakeholders, SPIDER seeks to empower sustainable actions that bolster EU-LAC cooperation in digital transformation and R&I.

The detailed insights and guidelines of this exploitation plan will be fully explained in the updated Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan v2 on M24.

5.1. Main Exploitable Results

Initially, we have identified several key exploitation results (KER) and the potential users.

KER	Exploitable results	Description of results	Potential Users
#1	Framework for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Conceptual framework to define the basis to implement the political outcomes of digital dialogues in view to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.	Digital dialogues' leaders, policy makers, NRENs, RPOs, RFOs, ICT and digital companies, BELLA network, GEANT community, LAC space agencies
#2	Position paper on pathways for the exploitation of BELLA infrastructure	The Position Paper outlines the strategy to exploit the full potential of BELLA beyond interconnectivity of the R&I communities from both sides of the Atlantic. The document includes priority areas and recommendations for EU-LAC digital transformation.	NRENs, RPOs, RFOs, ICT and digital companies, LAC space agencies, digital dialogues' leaders, policy makers
#3	EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF)	The DIF is a multi-stakeholder mechanism to promote policy debate and provide opinions and recommendations to implement the outcomes of EU-LAC digital dialogues.	Digital dialogues' leaders, policy makers, BELLA network, GEANT community, NRENs, RPOs, RFOs, LAC space agencies, ICT and digital companies

KER	Exploitable results	Description of results	Potential Users
#4	Twinning Programme for EU-LAC digital partnerships	Action Plans of twinned innovation hubs and services portfolio with best practices; Mentoring programme to companies, SMEs, and start-ups; and matchmaking between innovators and investors.	Digital and ICT companies, including SMEs, start-ups, digital innovation hubs, business developers and investors; BELLA network, ENRICH in LAC network, digital dialogues' leaders
#5	Roadmap for future EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	The roadmap will be a reference document for future steps towards EU-LAC cooperation in R&I. Also, it will provide input and recommendations for the EU-LAC strategic roadmap on STI developed in the framework of the EU-CELAC Joint Initiative on R&I.	Policy makers, NRENs, RPOs, RFOs, digital dialogues' leaders, ICT and digital companies, BELLA network, GEANT community, LAC space agencies

5.2. Exploitation Channels

In exploiting project results, each channel serves a specific role in disseminating information, fostering collaboration, and maximizing impact:

5.2.1. Website

The project website will act as a centralized repository for project results and resources. It will serve as a platform for showcasing project outcomes, providing stakeholders with easy access to relevant documents, reports, and multimedia content.

5.2.2. Social media channels

Social media platforms will serve as powerful tools for amplifying project visibility, engaging stakeholders, and driving traffic toward the website where the final exploitable results will be published. Through LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter) SPIDER will maximize its reach, foster community engagement, and generate interest in project outcomes.

5.2.3. Email campaigns

Email campaigns and newsletters will ease the efforts to maximize the awareness and involvement of the stakeholders in the outcomes of the project and foster ongoing communication, and engagement with project results.

5.2.4. Peer reviewed publications

Publishing project results in peer-reviewed journals and academic publications enhance the credibility and reach of SPIDER's outcomes. By sharing in-depth analyses, methodologies, and results with a specialized audience, peer-reviewed publications contribute to the broader discourse on digital transformation and EU-LAC cooperation. They establish SPIDER as a thought leader in the field, attracting collaboration opportunities and informing policy and practice.

6. ESTIMATED EXECUTION TIMELINE

The following is an estimated execution timeline of SPIDERS’s communication and dissemination activities. These actions, and the plan overall, will be updated and adapted as the project evolves.

6.1. Communication Estimated Timeline

Year 1: Launch and Connect											
M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Project Launch: Creation of website and custom social media channels			Present SPIDER and make it visible to relevant stakeholders, organizations, and partners to create synergies			Establish and fortify the project visibility while Introducing SPIDERS’s scope and objectives to partners’ professional and institutional networks			Promote the events of the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) and the Community of Practice in EU and LAC		
Year 2: Build Momentum											
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Promote first results on SPIDER’s website and social media channels			Publish results on partners’ institutional websites and social media networks. Promote dissemination of results at third-party events.			Promote the final mapping of digital dialogues and identified EU-LAC agreements, and other interim project results on SPIDERS and the partner website, social media, and third-party events			Promote the events of the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) and the Community of Practice in EU and LAC		
Year 3: Increase reach and positioning											
M25		M26		M27		M28		M29		M30	
Contact specialised and generalised media about interim project results		Launch email, social media, and web campaigns promoting the publication of project results and the final summit. Promote the DIF				Launch email, social media, and web campaigns promoting the publication of project results. Promote the DIF					

6.2. Dissemination Estimated Timeline

Year 1: Establish a robust foundation for dissemination											
M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Communication activities											
Year 2: Disseminating results to key stakeholders											
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M18	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Launch targeted email campaigns with interim project results to SPIDER’s list of key stakeholders			Present interim results at project events as well as third-party events			Present interim results at project events as well as third-party events			Launch targeted email campaigns to collect feedback on interim results and create engagement with the project		
Year 3: SPIDER’s positioning in high-impact channels											
M25		M26		M27		M28		M29		M30	
Continue to disseminate interim results at partners’ websites, third-party events, and SPIDER’s channels while announcing that final results will be presented soon				Publish results in targeted scientific and industry publications likely to be read by key stakeholder groups. Send results to SPIDER’s identified target audiences using high-impact channels				Host a final project summit and present final results and publications to a curated list of the project’s target audiences			

7. KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

To ensure SPIDER's Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan maximizes the project's impact and broadens its reach, we will assess its effectiveness using both quantitative and qualitative measures. If significant deviations occur, such as failing to meet objectives in three or more indicators, the consortium will adjust the plan and implement necessary measures to realign the project.

Nevertheless, recognizing the plan's dynamic nature, it will continuously evolve and be fine-tuned to suit the project's requirements.

Quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) are measurable using analytics tools, like website visits, while qualitative KPIs, such as community engagement and content responses, are less easily measurable.

Given that some channels serve communication, dissemination, and exploitation purposes, certain indicators will overlap in their strategies.

7.1. Communication KPIs

Communication KPIs aim to ensure the promotion of the project and enhance its visibility among key stakeholders. These actions serve as the foundation for dissemination efforts by informing stakeholders about the project's objectives and actions.

7.1.1. Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	Target
Social media followers (Twitter, LinkedIn)	3.000 followers (at least 1.200/year)
Newsletters	Launch a newsletter every 4 months. At least 3.000 subscribers by the end of the project.
Website visits	9.000 visits (at least 3.600/year)
Promotional actions on partners online channels	50 actions (at least 20/year)

7.1.2. Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	Target
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions on online channels.
Proactive online community	Community that engages with the project's content.
Contributions to other actions	Requests for contribution from the project can be seen as an example of its influence among stakeholders.

7.2. Dissemination KPIs

Dissemination aims to transfer project-generated knowledge to stakeholders that can benefit from it. Therefore, dissemination KPIs will focus on the transfer and engagement with project results.

7.2.1. Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	Target
Number of social media campaigns to promote project results	At least 6
Number of email campaigns, e.g., newsletters, project publications and event invitations for target groups	At least 30 (12/year)
Number of visits to the Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum	5.000 visits to DIF page (2.000/year)
Number of participants in SPIDER events	At least 250 direct participants

7.2.2. Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	Target
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions of project results on online channels.
Proactive online community	Scientific community that engages with project’s results and adds to the conversation.
Contributions to other actions	Requests for contribution, specifically project results, from the project can be seen as an example of its influence among stakeholders.

Annex 1 - Media Kit

About the logo and brand identity:

Based on the nature of the project and the fact that SPIDER holds at its core the values of **collaboration, innovation, inclusion, human-centered, sustainability, transparency, diversity, and digitalization**, we wanted our brand identity to be a reflection of the vision and values that we promote as a project while positioning **SPIDER as a link** between EU and LAC, and between technological development/ innovation and people/sustainability/diversity, inclusion, and equality.

Thus, we have selected the following logo since we believed that it better represented the spirit we wanted to transmit: *a sustainable and human-centered digital transformation.*

The selection of colors embodies a contemporary and technological essence. The chosen palettes symbolize modernity and convey a sense of innovation and technology. Furthermore, the chosen rounded and clean font reinforces a polished image.

In addition to the color and font choices, the isotype is a visual representation of SPIDER's human-centered and collaborative approach. Its design reflects our commitment to fostering connections and working collaboratively with a focus on people. This strategic combination of visual elements communicates our brand values effectively, positioning SPIDER as a forward-thinking and people-centric project.

Official colors

This is the official logo of the project

These are the color variations of the logo

These are the isotype

Acknowledging EU funding

This is crucial: "All communication related to the support and display the European flag and project, dissemination activities and any funding statement (translated into local infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or languages, where appropriate)."
 major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU [Find the logo here](#)

Recommendations for publications on social media

- Enhance engagement and relevance of content creation.
- Utilize bullet points and emojis to enhance the readability of publications.
- Share SPIDER's posts across personal social media profiles and motivate friends and family to interact with them.
- Engage with comments, messages, and mentions to cultivate a vibrant community.
- Incorporate pertinent hashtags to amplify discoverability.
- Tag the official social media accounts of SPIDER and other pertinent partners in your posts.
- Incorporate visually appealing images or designs that align with SPIDER's identity.
- Note: On LinkedIn, personal accounts typically enjoy a wider reach than corporate accounts.

Brand Stock Image Bank

Do you need images for your publications about SPIDER?

We created a Stock Image Bank with some images aligned with the brand's identity to maintain consistency, credibility, and resonance in the minds of our audiences. [Find the folder here](#)

Recommended Hashtags

- #SPIDERProject
- #HorizonEurope
- #DigitalTransformation
- #HorizonEU
- #digitalization
- #connectivity
- #EULAC
- #InternationalCooperation

Project Resources:

- 1) Access the shared folder "SPIDER_Consortium"

2) Access the folder "WP5 Communication & Dissemination"

3) Within the "WP5.Communication & Dissemination" folder you will find 3 folders: Partners Logos, SPIDER's Brand Identity, SPIDER's Colors, and SPIDER's templates.

4) Inside the "SPIDER's Brand Identity" folder we have:

- "funded by EU_EN" with all the official information needed to acknowledge EU funding. In case you ever need it.
- "Logo" with all the versions and formats of the logo.
- "Official Font" in case you need it for any specific design.
- "SPIDER's Colors" a pdf with the official brand colors.

- SPIDER Presentation Template
- SPIDER Deliverable Template.docx

5) Inside the "SPIDER's Templates" folder we will have: A **template for the deliverables** and another for the **presentation of the projects**.

Please remember to **follow the design guidelines** of each document.

Annex 2 – Background for online meetings

Annex 3 – Project presentation

SPIDER is a **European Union-funded project** that extends the longstanding tradition of collaboration between the European Union and Latin-American and the Caribbean concerning **digital transformation and R&I**.

Under the “**Innovate Together: EU-LAC Digital Partnership**” theme, SPIDER is actively unleashing the power of the **BELLA network** and bridging the gap between **EU-LAC digital dialogue commitments and their practical implementation**.

The **SPIDER** acronym stands for EU-LAC Strategic Partnership for the Implementation of Digital Dialogues in R&I Cooperation.

The project spans a duration of 30 months, from November 1, 2023, to April 30, 2026.

CONTEXT

- The **full potential of the BELLA network** and its infrastructure providing long-term interconnectivity between EU and LAC has not been fully exploited yet.
- LAC have a considerable **digital gap** that impacts harder in low-income population and vulnerable groups like women, especially in Central America countries where the economic, social, and infrastructure conditions differ from other neighbouring countries.
- The **lack of awareness of commitments and outcomes** undertaken in the context of multiple bilateral policy/sectoral dialogues on digital-related topics makes difficult their implementation on the ground, due to unfamiliarity with the content and incomplete alignment with national strategies.
- The **lack of a framework** to effectively implement and monitor the political outcomes and commitments resulting from existing EU-LAC digital dialogues hinders EU-LAC R&I cooperation.

OBJECTIVES

*“Laying the foundation where
innovation knows no bounds”*

EXPECTED RESULTS

- EU-LAC **Digital Dialogues Implementation** Forum (DIF)
- **Twinning Programme** for EU-LAC digital partnerships
- Roadmap for **future EU-LAC cooperation** on digital transformation.
- **Framework for EU-LAC** cooperation on digital transformation
- **Position paper on pathways** for the exploitation of BELLA infrastructure

IMPACT

- **Support implementation of commitments** related to R&I resulting from digital dialogues with key countries and sub-regional organisations in LAC.
- Develop a **roadmap for future R&I cooperation** with the LAC region and relevant national funding schemes for its application.
- Report on **synergies and commonalities in policies**, strategies and programmes related to R&I between the EU and partner countries.
- **Increased inclusiveness**, by supporting a human-centred approach to technology development that is aligned with European social and ethical values, as well as sustainability.
- **Promote EU values** for a human-centred digital transformation and contribute to Sustainable Development Goals.
- **Sustainable, high-quality jobs** by targeting skills mismatches, the need to empower workers, including those at risk of social exclusion, and ethical considerations relating to technological progress.

THE EU-LAC DIGITAL DIALOGUES IMPLEMENTATION FORUM (DIF)

The project's core actions include the **launch of the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF)**. This pioneering, multi-stakeholder platform is designed to foster dialogues, promote policy debate, and facilitate the implementation of R&I commitments from EU-LAC digital dialogues. This forum will host two working groups:

WORKING GROUP 1

Human-Centric digital transformation

WORKING GROUP 2

Diversity, Equality and Inclusion

Working Groups insights will contribute to **shape the roadmap and recommendations**, facilitating the implementation of EU-LAC dialogue commitments.

The SPIDER consortium combines the digital transformation and research and innovation (R&I) expertise of organizations from Spain, Portugal, Germany, Belgium, Chile, Ecuador, Brazil, and Costa Rica.